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Case of a Spontaneous, Low-Flow, Indirect Carotid-Cavernous Fistula as an Ophthalmological Manifestation of COVID-19

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Background: Here we present an interesting case of a spontaneous, low-flow, indirect carotid-cavernous fistula (CCF) secondary to COVID-19 infection.

Case report: A 75-year-old man was referred to the University Clinical Centre of Serbia Eye Hospital in November 2021 due to the acute visual loss followed by ophthalmoplegia and increasing eyelid swelling in the right eye (RE). He was previously treated elsewhere for 10 days under diagnosis of unilateral conjunctivitis but was found to be nonresponsive to prescribed Dexamethason-Neomycin eye drops. Previous head or eye trauma was not reported. However, he had a history of poorly controlled systemic arterial hypertension, diabetes and a triple bypass surgery. He had COVID-19 pneumonia in October 2021. Upon admission, he underwent a complete ophthalmological examination and diagnosis. BCVA was 20/20 in the left eye, with no light perception in the RE. There was both upper and lower eyelid swelling followed by upper eyelid ptosis, conjunctival chemosis, restricted eye movements in all directions of gaze and proptosis in the RE. Relative afferent papillary defect was also positive in the RE. CTA scans did not show an obvious fistula, however diffuse atherosclerotic changes in a form of alternating segmental dilatation and stenosis located in both intra and extracranial parts of ACI were described. At a 3-month follow up examination, a resolution of proptosis with a gradual improvement in ophthalmoplegia were present, however visual loss remains.

Conclusion: This case illustrates that CCF may develop spontaneously during COVID-19 infection due to more frequent thrombotic complications related to COVID infection.

Key words: CCF, COVID-19, thrombotic complications, early diagnosis

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The Fluorescence of Hair, Nails and Ocular Surface in COVID-19 Patients Following Favipiravir Treatment

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Background: Favipiravir is one of the medications currently approved for the treatment of COVID-19. The aim of our study was to present the fluorescence of nails, hair and ocular surface in patients who have received favipiravir for COVID-19 and to compare them with those who have received other drugs such as molnupiravir and remdesivir.

Case reports: The fluorescence was investigated under ultraviolet light (365 nm wavelength). The main ingredient thought to be responsible for the fluorescence of favipiravir is titanium dioxide. The fluorescent parts of the nails were proportionally elongated with the drug initiation time. Greenish fluorescence starting from the lunula and a nail plate portion near proximal nail fold was observed in two patients who have used the drug recently (Case 1 and 2), while in those who have received favipiravir over a month ago fluorescence could be observed in the middle portion of the nail plates with no fluorescence on the proximal part of the nail plates (Case 3 and 4). Green fluorescence could also be observed on the hair of patients treated with favipiravir. Previously reported ocular surface changes were not observed. No fluorescence was observed on the nails, hair and ocular surface in patients who have received molnupiravir or remdesivir.

Conclusion: Considering the fact that this substance accumulates in the tissues such as hair and nails, we should be careful when prescribing favipiravir especially for patients with known history of kidneys and liver dysfunction since they are among main targets of this medicine.

Key words: COVID-19, favipiravir, fluorescence, UV-A

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